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A PRISMA-BASED HYPERSENSPECTRAL DATASET FOR AGRICULTURE

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ABSTRACT

In this article we introduce a hyperspectral image dataset derived from PRISMA hyperspectral data, entitled HyDACI6. The dataset contains six cropped and filtered hyperspectral images acquired in 2024 over the area of interest to the North of Brasov City in Romania. The images were cropped to 700 × 700 pixels and the spectral bands corresponding to the atmosphere blocking were filtered out, resulting in 187 spectral bands out of the 239 original ones. The dataset contains the mask with the labels of the agricultural crops of the National Institute of Research and Development for Potato and Sugar Beet in Brasov. The HyDACI6 dataset is freely available as open data on Zenodo. We illustrate the usefulness of the proposed dataset with results on an agricultural crop identification application in agriculture.

Index Terms: PRISMA, hyperspectral images, crop identification

1. INTRODUCTION

The estimated growth of the world population [1] puts a high demand on agriculture. Consequently, it becomes vital to optimize the resource usage in agriculture [2] [3] [4]. Smart agriculture, defined by the deployment of artificial intelligence (AI)-based tools, can be able to provide solutions to this problem [5]. Recently, studies on using AI and smart systems for agricultural crop monitoring have been proposed [6]. One major limitation in using and fully adopting at a larger scale the AI models, in particular machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) models, is the lack of large amount of labeled data for training such data. This is the prerequisite for accurate detection and classification [7]. Freely available labeled data is not sufficient [8]. In addition, for data sets on agriculture, labels usually rely on declarations from farmers, which sometimes may not be correct, introducing biases in the resulting learning-based models [9]. Despite the fact that ML and DL models can still generalize from erroneous data/labels, their robustness is limited [10]. Several data sets of Earth observation do exist for applications in agriculture. One of them is BigEarthNet [11], comprising Sentinel-2 image patches from 10 European countries. BigEarthNet is designed for multi-label image classification for land cover, but it lacks detailed and verified crop type annotations. EuroSAT [12] provides a dataset based on Sentinel-2 data for land use and land cover classification. The dataset includes agricultural areas, but it lacks the specific crop type information and multi-temporal data necessary for the identification and monitoring of crops. The SEN12MS dataset [13] is based on Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 data, but is not primarily designed for agriculture, missing accurate crop labels over multiple years. The CropHarvest dataset [14] is a global-scale repository for crop type classification, aggregating data from multiple sources. However,

¹ Available on Zenodo at: <https://zenodo.org/records/15830646>

CropHarvest frequently relies on crowd-sourced labels and consequently lacks the required level of accuracy for precision agriculture. In addition, the dataset exhibits inconsistencies in temporal coverage and spatial resolution. The TimeSen2Crop [15] is a pixel-based dataset, including more than a million labeled multispectral Sentinel-2 pixels collected across Austria over two consecutive years. It provides labels for 16 different crop types, but they are based on farmers' declarations which can be less accurate. The PASTIS [16] data set is based on both Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 data, providing 2.433 patches (128 ×128 pixels)/time series and the corresponding labels for the French metropolitan territory. A more recent data set is DACIA5 [17], which comprises the Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 data, in approximately 6k patches of (32 ×32 pixels) over a period of 5 years for the agricultural crops of the National Institute of Research and Development for Potato and Sugar Beet (in short, Potato Institute), Brasov, Romania. In this paper, we introduce HyDACIA61 data set which contains six hyperspectral images derived from the PRISMA mission data from year 2024 over the north area of Braşov city, Romania, comprising the crops of the Potato Institute. The data set also includes a mask and the crop legend. We illustrate the usefulness of the data set for crop identification.

2. PROPOSED DATASET

2.1. DATA ACQUISITION

The HyDACI6 dataset comprises six hyperspectral images derived from the data acquired by the PRISMA (Hyperspectral Precursor and Application Mission) satellite of the Italian Space Agency (ASI), covering a specific area of Brasov, Romania for the year 2024. The PRISMA sensor features a hyperspectral imaging system with a spatial resolution of 30 meters and operates in two spectral ranges: a visible and near-infrared (VNIR) band consisting of 66 channels spanning 400–1010 nm, and a shortwave infrared (SWIR) band comprising 173 channels covering the 920–2505 nm range. For each image in the dataset we provide the color RGB composites using the AI-based visualization in [18], also shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Visualization of the PRISMA images using AI [18].

2.2. DATA PREPROCESSING

The images in HyDACI6 are cropped from the original PRISMA products to 700 ×700 ×187, specifically, having a height of 700 pixels, a width of 700 pixels, and 187 spectral bands, with a spatial resolution of 30 meters. Originally, PRISMA images have 239 spectral bands, but we eliminated the water absorption bands and kept only the spectral information of interest. Concretely, we removed the bands 99-

108, 143-164 and 220- 230, corresponding to the wavelength ranges [1349.8–1449.2 nm], [1813.1–2002.1 nm] and [2276.1–2349.8 nm]. The six images were acquired in March, May, June, July, and October 2024, ensuring clear observation of all parcels belonging to the Potato Institute. All the images respect a naming convention where the level of processing and the data of acquisition are specified.

2.3. DATA ANNOTATION

For the parcels of interest, we generated a mask to include all the parcels belonging to the Potato Institute. The exact information regarding the agricultural crops (labels) was provided by the Potato Institute, thus are exact and error-free. In this mask, the parcels are represented with the specific color for each type of crop. The color palette for the agricultural crops was adopted from the one provided by the United States Department of Agriculture. A detailed, zoomed in version of this mask can be seen in the Figure 2. In the dataset we provide the full color mask, the labels mask, the legend for the masks and the wavelengths for the 187 spectral bands of interest.

Fig. 2. The color mask for the crops in 2024 (left); overlaid on the RGB composite (right).

All the existing datasets enumerated in the introduction are based on Sentinel-2 data, thus are multi-spectral. The HyDAC16 data set is, as far as we are aware, a unique hyper-spectral dataset, spanning over a full agricultural season (with six acquisition dates) that enables applications in agriculture.

3. USE CASE AND EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In this section we present a use case of crop identification to demonstrate the applicability of the dataset within the context of smart agriculture. Similar to the studies by [19] and [20], where 1D convolutional models were employed for hyper-spectral image classification, we chose to use a 1D Residual Network (ResNet) for our experiments on the image data acquired on 14 May 2024. We choose a total of five classes for the identification task - three classes corresponding to the agricultural crops available in May 2024, the fourth one is bare soil and the fifth one for other type of vegetation, which was chosen to be forest. These classes and colours for their representation and easier identification in the scene can be seen in Table 1.

Class	Colour
winter wheat	green
rapeseed	red
peas	yellow
bare soil	cyan
forest	blue

Table 1. Classes for the identification task.

Fig. 3. Detailed, zoomed-in views of the parcels used as training (left) and testing (right) data on the 14 May 2024 image.

The data was split in training and testing, this split can be seen illustrated in Figure 3, showing the parcels/regions that were used for training and the ones for testing. We defined a custom 1D ResNet architecture, depicted in Figure 4. The network takes as input data a single hyperspectral pixel of 187 values. The network has an initial convolutional block that acts as a feature extractor. The core of the network consists of two residual blocks, each comprising a main path of two convolutional layers, batch normalization, and ReLU activation functions. Each residual block incorporates a skip connection. The architecture ends with a global average pooling layer that reduces the spatial dimensions, followed by a fully connected layer for classification into five classes, and finally, softmax and classification layers.

Fig. 4. The architecture of the deployed 1D ResNet network.

The network was trained using the Adam optimizer with an initial learning rate of 10^{-3} over 40 epochs. During training, data is processed in mini-batches of size 64 and shuffled at every epoch to ensure better generalization. The training data consists of the pixels corresponding for 14 parcels/regions, each parcel corresponding to a certain class. The test data, different from the training data, consists of the pixel corresponding to 5 parcels/regions belonging to the five classes (as in Figure 3). The result can be seen in Figure 5.

Fig. 5. Segmentation on the entire image from May 14. The legend for the image is in the Table 1.

In order to assess the accuracy of the identification and, implicitly, the resulting segmentation we considered and computed four quality measures: border error (BE) [21], Jaccard index [22], rand index (RI or accuracy) [23] and Dice coefficient [22]. The BE was calculated as $BE = \frac{\text{Area}((A \cup M) - A \cap M)}{\text{Area}(M)}$, where A represents the crop areas obtained after the segmentation and M are the manually segmented regions (from the ground truth). The results are presented in Table 2. For the classes winter wheat and bare soil, the identification and, thus, the segmentation of the regions gives the best results, while for rapeseed, peas and forest the identification is around 99%.

Crop type	Jaccard(%)	RI(%)	F1 score(%)	BE
winter wheat	1	1	1	0
rapeseed	0.99	1	0.99	0.004
peas	0.98	1	0.99	0.014
bare soil	1	1	1	0
forest	0.98	1	0.99	0.016

Table 2. Segmentation accuracy assessment.

However, the classification results can be highly impacted by a set of parameters such as meteorological parameters, climate-related data, soil characteristics etc. It is known that, for instance, the classification of agricultural crops based on NDVI time series can be affected by the temperature (and other parameters), as the study [24] shows a high correlation coefficient between NDVI and temperature time series. The classification of agricultural crops enables the agricultural decision-making applications, such as yield prediction and resource optimization (e.g. by using Variable-Rate Application of water or nutrients).

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this article we introduced a hyperspectral image dataset entitled HyDACI6 - Hyperspectral Dataset for Agricultural Crop Identification. HyDACI6 is based on data derived from the PRISMA hyperspectral data, kindly provided by the Italian Space Agency, ASI. The dataset contains six cropped hyperspectral images, of size 700 × 700 pixels, acquired in the year 2024 over the area of interest to the North of

Brasov City in Romania. From the original 239 spectral bands of the PRISMA data, we removed the spectral bands corresponding to the atmosphere blocking, resulting in 187 spectral bands for the images in the dataset. The HyDACI6 dataset contains the mask with the labels of the agricultural crops of the National Institute of Research and Development for Potato and Sugar Beet in Brasov. The HyDACI6 dataset is available as open data on Zenodo. We illustrated the usefulness of the proposed dataset in an agricultural crop identification application for agriculture. We chose the image from 14 May 2024 and used a 1D ResNet model to be trained on the data from 14 parcels/regions corresponding to 5 classes: winter wheat, rapeseed, peas, bares soil and forest. The trained model was tested on the data from 5 parcels/region and the performance was evaluated on the final segmentation map by using four metrics. From our experiments, all the five classes were perfectly or almost perfectly identified and, consequently, segmented, with respect to the ground truth. For the future work, we are considering an early crop identification scenario, in which we train the AI model with data from the image acquired in May 2024 and test on the data from the one acquired in June 2024. Also, adding the temporal component and experiment with time series for the crop identification application, in order to fully benefit of the available data in the HyDACI6 data set.

5. REFERENCES

- [1] H. Ritchie and L. Rodes-Guirao, "Peak global population and other key findings from the 2024 world population prospects," *Our World in Data*, 2024.
- [2] R. Anderson, P. E Bayer, and D. Edwards, "Climate change and the need for agricultural adaptation," *Current Opinion in Plant Biology*, vol. 56, pp. 197–202, 2020.
- [3] D. Frona, J. Szenderak, and M. Harangi-Rakos, "The challenge of feeding the world," *Sustainability*, vol. 11, no. 20, 2019.
- [4] M. M. Maja and S. F. Ayano, "The impact of population growth on natural resources and farmers' capacity to adapt to climate change in low-income countries," *Earth Systems and Environment*, vol. 5, pp. 271 – 283, 2021.
- [5] M. Ivanovici, G. Olteanu, C. Florea, R. M. Coliban, M. S , tefan, and K. Marandskiy, *Digital Transformation in Agriculture*, pp. 157–191, Springer Nature Switzerland, Cham, 2024.
- [6] Y. Akkem, S. K. Biswas, and A. Varanasi, "Smart farming using artificial intelligence: A review," *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence*, vol. 120, pp. 105899, 2023.
- [7] E. Benami, Z. Jin, M. R. Carter, A. Ghosh, R. J. Hijmans, A. Hobbs, B. Kipkemboi Kenduiywo, and D. Lo-bell, "Uniting remote sensing, crop modelling and economics for agricultural risk management," *Nature Reviews Earth & Environment*, vol. 2, pp. 140 – 159, 2021.
- [8] L. Alzubaidi, J. Bai, A. Al-Sabaawi, J. I. Santamaría, A. S. Albahri, B. S. N. Al-dabbagh, M. A. Fadhel, M. Manoufali, J. Zhang, A. H. Al-timemy, Y. Duan, A. Abdullah, L. Farhan, Y. Lu, A. Gupta, F. Albu, A. Abbosh, and Y. Gu, "A survey on deep learning tools dealing with data scarcity: definitions, challenges, solutions, tips, and applications," *Journal of Big Data*, vol. 10, pp. 1–82, 2023.
- [9] G. F. Cabrera, C. J. Miller, and J. Schneider, "Systematic labeling bias: De-biasing where everyone is wrong," in *2014 22nd International Conference on Pattern Recognition*, 2014, pp. 4417–4422.
- [10] H. Song, M. Kim, D. Park, Y. Shin, and J.G. Lee, "Learning from noisy labels with deep neural networks: A survey," *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems*, vol. 34, no. 11, pp. 8135–8153, 2023.
- [11] G. Sumbul, M. Charfuelan, B. Demir, and V. Markl, "Bigearthnet: A large-scale benchmark archive for remote sensing image understanding," in *IGARSS 2019 - 2019 IEEE International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium*, 2019, pp. 5901–5904.

- [12] P. Helber, B. Bischke, A. Dengel, and D. Borth, "Eu-rosat: A novel dataset and deep learning benchmark for land use and land cover classification," *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Applied Earth Observations and Remote Sensing*, vol. 12, no. 7, pp. 2217–2226, 2019.
- [13] M. Schmitt, L. H. Hughes, C. Qiu, and X. X. Zhu, "Sen12ms – a curated dataset of georeferenced multi-spectral sentinel-1/2 imagery for deep learning and data fusion," *ISPRS Annals of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences*, vol. IV-2/W7, pp. 153–160, 2019.
- [14] G. Tseng, I. Zvonkov, C. Nakalembe, and H. Kerner, "Cropharvest: A global dataset for crop-type classification," in *Proceedings of the Neural Information Processing Systems Track on Datasets and Benchmarks*, J. Vanschoren and S. Yeung, Eds., 2021, vol. 1.
- [15] G. Weikmann, C. Paris, and L. Bruzzone, "Time-sen2crop: A million labeled samples dataset of sentinel 2 image time series for crop-type classification," *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Applied Earth Observations and Remote Sensing*, vol. 14, pp. 4699–4708, 2021.
- [16] V. Sainte Fare Garnot, L. Landrieu, and N. Chehata, "Multi-modal temporal attention models for crop mapping from satellite time series," *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing*, vol. 187, pp. 294–305, 2022.
- [17] A. Băicoianu, I. C. Plajer, M. Debu, M. Ștefan, M. Ivanovici, C. Florea, A. Cațaron, R. M. Coliban, Ș. Popa, Ș. Opreșcu, A. Racovițeanu, Gh. Olteanu, K. Marandskiy, A. Ghinea, A. Kazak, L. Majercsik, A. Manea, and L. Dogar, "Dacia5: a sentinel-1 and sentinel-2 dataset for agricultural crop identification applications," *Big Earth Data*, pp. 1–32, 2025.
- [18] I. C. Plajer, A. Băicoianu, L. Majercsik, and M. Ivanovici, "Multisource remote sensing data visualization using machine learning," *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 62, pp. 1–12, 2024.
- [19] Mayar A. Shafaey, Farid Melgani, Mohammed A.-M. Salem, Maryam N. Al-Berry, Hala M. Ebied, El-Sayed A. El-Dahshan, and Mohamed F. Tolba, "Pixel-wise classification of hyperspectral images with 1d convolutional svm networks," *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 133174–133185, 2022.
- [20] X. Hu, W. Yang, H. Wen, Y. Liu, and Y. Peng, "A lightweight 1-d convolution augmented transformer with metric learning for hyperspectral image classification," *Sensors*, vol. 21, no. 5, 2021.
- [21] S. Zambanini, R. Sablatnig, H. Maier, and G. Langs, "Automatic image-based assessment of lesion development during hemangioma follow-up examinations," *Artificial Intelligence in Medicine*, vol. 50, no. 2, pp. 83–94, 2010.
- [22] I. Ataș, "Performance evaluation of jaccard-dice coefficient on building segmentation from high resolution satellite images," *Balkan Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 100–106, 2023.
- [23] H. Nghi, "Understanding evaluation metrics in medical image segmentation," 2023, Accessed: Mar 2, 2023.
- [24] M. Ivanovici, M. Ștefan, A. Cațaron, A. Ghinea, and G. Olteanu, "Analyzing the influence of temperature on ndvi for a potato crop in brasov area," *Land Reclamation, Earth Observation Surveying, Environmental Engineering*, 06 2025.

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